

Experimental Investigation and Optimization of Welding Parameters for SAE 1020 and SS 303

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Abstract:

In this study, the optimization of welding parameters for dissimilar joints of SAE 1020 and SS 303 using the Manual Metal Arc Welding (MMAW) process is investigated. The research aims to enhance the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) by employing the Taguchi method and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to analyze and optimize critical welding parameters: welding current, welding speed, root gap, and joint angle. Experiments were conducted following an L9 orthogonal array using Minitab 19 software, and a regression model was developed to predict UTS based on these parameters. The findings indicate that welding speed is the most significant factor influencing UTS, followed by root gap and welding current. Optimal parameter settings were identified, resulting in a maximum UTS value closely matching the predicted outcome with a minimal error margin of 2.59%. This study demonstrates the efficacy of statistical methods in optimizing welding conditions for achieving enhanced mechanical properties in dissimilar metal welding applications.

Keywords: MMAW, Taguchi Method, ANOVA, UTS.

1.INTRODUCTION

Welding is fundamental in modern industries such as construction, automotive, and manufacturing, providing robust and durable joints in various materials. Among welding techniques, Manual Metal Arc Welding (MMAW), also known as Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW), remains one of the most widely used methods due to its versatility, low cost, and adaptability in different environments. It utilizes a consumable electrode and a gaseous shield to create welds, making it effective in diverse settings, particularly in outdoor and variable conditions.

Despite its advantages, MMAW presents challenges such as slower welding speeds due to frequent electrode changes and additional time required for slag removal, impacting overall productivity. Recent studies emphasize the need to optimize welding parameters to minimize these drawbacks while enhancing the mechanical properties of weld joints.

Research on dissimilar metal welding, particularly between SAE 1020, a low-carbon steel known for its weldability, and SS 303, an austenitic stainless steel with excellent corrosion resistance, has gained attention. The combination of these materials creates a joint that balances strength and corrosion resistance, suitable for demanding applications in the automotive and aerospace industries. However, due to the differing thermal and mechanical properties of these metals, optimizing welding parameters is crucial to minimize residual stresses and ensure weld quality.

This study employs the Taguchi method and ANOVA to identify and optimize critical process parameters such as welding current, speed, root gap, and joint angle. By leveraging these statistical tools, this research aims to provide insights into the optimal settings for enhancing the UTS of SAE 1020 and SS 303 joints. The outcomes of this study contribute to the understanding of welding dissimilar materials and offer practical solutions for improving welding efficiency and strength in industrial applications.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

2.1. Methodology

For this project, after conducting the related literature survey we found that the among the most important parameters were current, weld speed, weld angle and root gap while keeping the other parameter constant. So, these four variables were used as treatment variables for the model. The following order of plan to optimize the process parameters for MS SAE and SS-303 material joints are detailed below:

1. Determination of critical process control parameters
2. Selecting the levels of the process control parameters
3. Selection of the experimental design matrix
4. Conducting the experiments as per the design matrix and recording of responses
5. Calculate the signal to noise (S/N) ratios
6. Analysis of variance (ANOVA)
7. Pooled ANOVA
8. Confirmatory test to check the optimized process parameters

2.2. Experimental Machine Selection

Experiments were conducted using an MMAW setup at Deogiri Institute of Engineering and Management Studies, Aurangabad, India. The equipment was calibrated to maintain consistency across trials. The levels for each parameter were determined based on industry guidelines and preliminary tests.

Figure 1: MMAW Welding Machine

2.3. Selecting the levels of the process control parameters

Based on a literature review mainly Mathi Kannaiyan et al (2020) and Jagwinderjit Singh Gill et al (2017) and the welding characteristics of SAE 1020 and SS 303, four key parameters were identified as crucial to influencing ultimate tensile strength (UTS):

- Welding Current: 80, 100, 120 A
- Welding Speed: 20, 40, 60 cm/min
- Root Gap: 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 mm
- Joint Angle: 45, 60, 90 degrees

Table 1: Levels of Input Parameters

Sr. No	Level 1	Level 2	Level 2
Welding Current (A)	80	100	120
Welding Speed(cm/min)	20	40	60
Root Gap (mm)	1.0	1.5	2.0
Joint Angle (degree)	45	60	90

These parameters were chosen because they directly impact the weld pool, heat input, and subsequent cooling rates, which are essential in determining the quality of dissimilar metal welds. Previous studies have shown that precise control of these factors significantly affects mechanical properties, including tensile strength and ductility.

2.4. Selection of the experimental design matrix

While there are many standard orthogonal matrices available, each of the matrices is intended for a specific number of variables and independent design levels.

The standard notation for orthogonal arrays is,
 $L_n(X_m)$

Where, n = Number of experiments to be conducted

X = Number of levels

m = Number of factors

Table 2 shows an orthogonal L_9 matrix. A total of nine experiments (experiments) will be conducted and each experiment is based on the combination of the level values shown in the table. In this study, the Taguchi L_9 OA is used with repetitions of the repeated reaction method to record the data of the experimental results. Repeated measurements are taken during the same experimental tests.

Table 2: Standards L_9 Orthogonal Array

Sr. No	Welding Current	Welding Speed	Root Gap	Angle
1	80	20	1.0	45
2	80	40	1.5	60
3	80	60	2.0	90
4	100	20	1.5	90
5	100	40	2.0	45
6	100	60	1.0	60
7	120	20	2.0	60
8	120	40	1.0	90
9	120	60	1.5	45

2.5. Selection of material

SAE 1020 and SS 303 are well-suited for dissimilar welding due to their distinct chemical compositions and complementary mechanical properties. SAE 1020 is a low-carbon steel, which enhances its weldability and reduces

the likelihood of hardening or cracking during the welding process. In contrast, SS 303, an austenitic stainless steel, offers excellent corrosion resistance and strength, thanks to its chromium and nickel content. The unique microstructure formed at the weld interface combines the toughness of the steel with the corrosion resistance of the stainless steel, creating a joint that performs well in demanding environments. Both materials can be welded using various techniques, such as MIG and TIG, although careful selection of filler materials is essential to achieve optimal results. Additionally, the differences in thermal expansion rates between the two metals can lead to residual stresses if not managed properly; therefore, controlling heat input and employing techniques like staggered welding can help mitigate these issues. This combination of materials is frequently used in applications such as automotive components, aerospace structures, and machinery parts, where strength, lightweight design, and resistance to environmental factors are critical. Overall, with the right techniques and considerations, dissimilar welding of SAE 1020 and SS 303 can yield reliable and durable joints suitable for a variety of applications.

SAE 1020 and SS-303

Table 3: Mechanical Properties

Mechanical Properties	SAE 1020	SS-303
Brinell Hardness,	121	230
Ultimate Tensile Strength,	420 MPa	435 MPa
Yield Tensile Strength,	350 MPa	370MPa
Break at Elongation	15.0 %	20.0 %
Modulus of Elasticity	205 GPa	29700 ksi
Poisson's Ratio	0.290	0.25
Shear Modulus	80 GPa	77.2 GPa

Table 4: Chemical Composition

Element	SAE 1020	SS 303
C	0.15	0.18
P	0.06	0.040
Mn	2.0	0.30
Mo	0.6	0.38
Ni	9.0	0.15
Si	0.98	0.10
S	0.15	0.05

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To gain a comprehensive understanding of how input parameters such as weld current, weld voltage, and gas flow rate impact the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of welded joints, it is essential to analyze the data using statistical methods. One effective approach is to assess the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N ratio) or create main effects plots for the means of these parameters. This analysis allows for a clearer visualization of how each factor influences UTS and identifies optimal settings for achieving desired strength characteristics.

For this analysis, Minitab 19 statistical software has been employed, leveraging its robust capabilities for conducting statistical tests and modeling. The first step involved performing an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to evaluate the significance of each input parameter's effect on UTS. ANOVA helps in determining whether the variations in UTS can be attributed to the changes in the input parameters or if they arise from random noise. This step is crucial in isolating the effects of each parameter, enabling us to understand which ones contribute most significantly to the overall weld strength.

In addition to ANOVA, a linear regression model has been established to predict UTS values based on the input parameters. This model provides a mathematical representation of the relationships between the weld current, voltage, and gas flow rate, allowing for predictions of UTS under varying conditions. By integrating the insights from both the ANOVA and regression analysis, we can develop a more nuanced understanding of how to optimize welding processes for improved material strength. This comprehensive approach not only enhances our understanding of the factors affecting weld quality but also supports informed decision-making in industrial applications, leading to better product outcomes.

3.1. Experimental results and corresponding S/N ratios

Table 5: shows the L9 orthogonal array with measurement of UTS for runs one to nine. It also shows S/N ratio for all nine experiments.

Experiments	Inputs Factors				Output Responses	
Trial No.	Welding Current	Welding Speed	Root Gap	Angle	UTS	S/N Ratio
1	80	20	1.0	45	452.17	53.1060
2	80	40	1.5	60	511.73	54.3489
3	80	60	2.0	90	459.56	53.4338
4	100	20	1.5	90	434.78	52.7654
5	100	40	2.0	45	437.39	52.4108
6	100	60	1.0	60	473.04	53.4980
7	120	20	2.0	60	486.95	53.7497
8	120	40	1.0	90	469.56	53.4338
9	120	60	1.5	45	509.13	54.6339

L₉ orthogonal array with repeated measurement of responses for runs one to nine. Using response back test technology overcomes the shortcomings of MINITAB software saturation design.

3.2. Main Effects of UTS

Figure 2: Main Effects Plot for S/N Ratio

A higher SN ratio with better characteristics was used and was calculated with the help of the MINITAB software for the experimental tests., it is observed that the optimum material removal rate was in the lowest values of the in the response graph. The optimal input parameters were Welding Current 120A (level 3), Welding Speed 60 cm/min (level 3). Root gap 1.5mm (level2) and Angle 60 degree (level 1). The graph graphically shows the effect of the control factors on SAE 1020 and SS-303 material. Parameter configuration process with the highest rate Remember to give the best with slight changes. The graph shows the relationship change when the control factor configuration was changed from one level to another.

3.3. Analysis of Variance Result

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted at a 95% confidence level to evaluate the influence of the specified process parameters on tensile strength. The primary objective of this statistical method is to determine which parameters significantly impact the response variable, in this case, tensile strength. By isolating the total deviation from the signal-to-noise ratio—quantified as the sum of squared deviations from all points of the signal-to-noise ratio—ANOVA allows for the assessment of each parameter's contribution, including any associated errors. ANOVA operates by comparing the variance within each experimental group to the variance between groups, providing insight into how different parameter combinations affect the tensile strength. The Fisher test, also known as the F-test, was employed to assess the statistical significance of the differences observed among the various experimental conditions. This method is particularly effective in determining whether the means of diverse groups are significantly different from one another.\

The results of the ANOVA analysis are summarized in the accompanying table, which details the contributions of each parameter to the overall variability in tensile strength. Notably, the analysis indicates that the p-values associated with the three primary parameter sources are less than 0.05. This threshold is crucial, as it suggests a statistically significant effect of these parameters on the tensile strength, allowing us to reject the null hypothesis that states there are no differences among group means.

In conclusion, the ANOVA results provide robust evidence of the significant influence that the selected process parameters exert on tensile strength. This understanding not only enhances our knowledge of the welding process but also aids in optimizing parameters to achieve desired material properties. The statistical rigor applied through ANOVA underscores the importance of data-driven decision-making in engineering practices, facilitating more informed approaches to process optimization.

Table 6: ANOVA Result.

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value	% Contribution
Welding Current		0.75112	0.37556	6.29	0.024	27.31
Welding Speed	2	1.12668	0.56334	9.44	0.016	40.96
Root Gap	2	0.37556	0.18778	3.14	0.048	13.65
Angle	2	0.37739	0.18869	3.16	0.048	13.72
Residual Error		0.11934				4.35
Total	8	2.75010				

Table shows the ANOVA of SAE 1020 and SS-303. The table shows that the Welding Current (27.31%), the welding speed (40.96%) and the Root gap (13.65%) and angle (13.72%) have a major influence on the UTS.

3.4. Development of Linear Regression Models

Mathematical models of welding speed, current, root gap and angle are calculated using MINITAB 19 software and analysis of regression conducted to obtain the predicted value of UTS.

Regression Equation –

$$\text{UTS} = 430 + 0.435 \text{ Welding Current} + 0.899 \text{ Welding Speed} - 7.0 \text{ Root Gap} - 0.392 \text{ Angle}$$

Table 7: Experimental and Predicted Values of UTS

Sr. No.	Experimental value	Predicted value	Error %
1	452.17	458.14	1.30
2	511.73	466.74	9.63
3	459.56	469.46	2.10
4	434.78	445.70	2.45
5	437.39	477.82	8.86
6	473.04	496.92	4.80

7	486.95	462.66	5.25
8	469.56	475.88	1.32
9	509.13	508.02	1.16

Difference between ultimate tensile strength values calculated using regression equation and experimental values for each experience found less than 10%. Therefore, we can say that the regression equation is valid. Figure 3 shows the graphical representation of experimental, and values calculated using regression equation.

Figure 3: Experimental Vs. Predicted UTS

Ultimate tensile strength decreases for first sample and increases for ninth sample because of Experiment from 1-9 are the set of experiments from Taguchi design L9 array; every experiment has different level of parameters and having unique combination of parameter level.

3.5. Confirmation Experiment Result

Experiments was conducted for Welding Current (level 3), Welding Speed (level 3), Root gap (level 2) and Angle (level 2)

Table 6: Confirmation Experiment Result

Parameter	Experimental value	Predicted value	Error %
UTS	515.48	502.12	2.59

A confirmation experiment is conducted to validate the effectiveness of the parameters identified as optimal through the Taguchi method. In this experiment, the welding parameters—weld current, weld voltage, and gas flow rate—are set at the optimal levels determined in previous analyses. The objective is to measure the ultimate tensile

strength (UTS) of the welded joints under these conditions and to compare the experimental results with those predicted by the previously established linear regression model.

After conducting the experiment, the obtained UTS value is found to differ from the predicted value by only 2.59%. This minimal difference indicates a strong correlation between the experimental results and the estimates provided by the regression model. Such a close alignment not only demonstrates the accuracy of the regression model but also reinforces the validity of the optimal parameters identified through the Taguchi method.

This confirmation experiment serves a dual purpose: it not only verifies the robustness of the statistical analyses conducted earlier but also instills confidence in the application of these findings in practical welding scenarios. By achieving a UTS value that closely matches the predicted outcome, we can conclude that the methodologies employed—both Taguchi optimization and regression analysis—are effective tools for enhancing welding quality. This correlation emphasizes the reliability of using statistical methods for process optimization in manufacturing, leading to improved product performance and consistency in industrial applications.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the effects of welding parameters on the tensile strength of SAE 1020 and SS 303 materials using the MMAW process. By employing the Taguchi method and ANOVA, critical parameters were optimized to enhance the UTS of the dissimilar weld. The findings highlight the importance of welding speed as the most influential parameter, followed by welding current, root gap, and joint angle.

The optimal configuration—welding current of 120 A, speed of 60 cm/min, root gap of 1.5 mm, and a joint angle of 45 degrees—resulted in the highest UTS, with a minimal error margin between experimental and predicted values, validating the developed regression model. This study contributes to the field of welding engineering by providing a systematic approach for optimizing dissimilar metal welding processes, ensuring strong, reliable joints suitable for demanding applications.

Future research can extend these findings by exploring the impact of different welding techniques (e.g., MIG, TIG) and other material combinations to develop a broader understanding of optimizing dissimilar welds. Additionally, incorporating advanced modeling techniques such as Response Surface Methodology (RSM) could further refine the optimization process and provide more comprehensive insights.

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6. REFERENCES

- [1] K. Srinivasulu Reddy, "Optimization and Prediction of Welding Parameters and Bead Geometry in Submerged Arc Welding," *Int. J. Appl. Eng. Res. Dev.*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 1–6, 2013.
- [2] M. S. C., B. R. Narendra Babu, B. S. Praveen Kumar, and Y. Vijayakumar, "Optimization of Shielded Metal Arc Welding Parameters for Welding of Pipes by Using Taguchi Approach," *Int. J. Eng. Res. Appl.*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 1460–1465, 2013.
- [3] N. Kiaee and M. Aghaie-Khafri, "Optimization of gas tungsten arc welding process by response surface methodology," *Materials and Design*, vol. 54, pp. 25–31, 2014.

- [4] O. Osayi, E. A. P. Egbe, and S. A. Lawal, "Optimization of Process Parameters of Manual Arc Welding of Mild Steel Using Taguchi Method," *Am. J. Mech. Eng.*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 93–97, 2015.
- [5] M. A. Moradpour, S. H. Hashemi, and K. Khalili, "Multi-objective Optimization of Welding Parameters in Submerged Arc Welding of API X65 Steel Plates," *J. Iron Steel Res. Int.*, vol. 22, no. 9, pp. 870–878, 2015.
- [6] D. S. Jadoun, R. P. Kori, and D. K. Kasdekar, "Optimization of Welding Parameter for Arc Welding of Mild Steel Plate (Grade-40)," no. 1, pp. 13–16, 2016.
- [7] G. Singh and S. K. Sharma, "Optimization of Submerged Arc Welding Process: A Review," *Int. J. Adv. Res. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 459–464, 2016.
- [8]*Jagwinderjit Singh Gill, Sukhwinder Singh Jolly, Charanjit Singh Kalra, "Multi Response Optimization TIG welding parameters for dissimilar weld of MONEL 400 and AISI 304 using RSM,IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IOSR-JMCE) E-ISSN: 2278-1684, p-ISSN: 2320-334X, Volume 14, Issue 4 Ver. II, 2017
- [9] M. V. Patil, "Multi response simulation and optimization of gas tungsten arc welding," *Appl. Math. Model.*, vol. 42, pp. 540–553, 2017.
- [10] W. Yan, H. Zhang, Z. gang Jiang, and K. K. B. Hon, "Multi-objective optimization of arc welding parameters: the trade-offs between energy and thermal efficiency," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 140, pp. 1842–1849, 2017.
- [11] A. A. Shukla, V. S. Joshi, A. Chel, and B. A. Shukla, "Analysis of Shielded metal arc welding parameter on Depth of Penetration on AISI 1020 plates using Response surface methodology," *Procedia Manuf.*, vol. 20, pp. 239–246, 2018.
- [12] A. A. Sheikh and P. D. Kamble, "Optimization of welding process parameter to minimize defect in welding of sheet," *Int. Res. J. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 4310–4314, 2018.
- [13] N. Ghosh, P. Kumar Pal, G. Nandi, and R. Rudrapati, "Parametric Optimization of Gas metal arc welding process by PCA based Taguchi method on Austenitic Stainless Steel AISI 316L," *Mater. Today, Proc.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1620–1625, 2018.
- [14]Mathi Kannaiyan, Jinu Gowthami, Thankachi Raghuvaran et al, "Process parameters and properties of electric resistance spot welded AISI304-AISI1020 dissimilar weldments" *Journal of Ceramic Processing Research*. Vol. 21, No. 1, pp. 26~34 (2020)
- [15]A. Choudhary, M. Kumar, and D. R. Unune, "Experimental investigation and optimization of weld bead characteristics during submerged arc welding of AISI 1023 steel," *Def. Technol.*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 72–82, 2019.
- [16] Ashok Pandarinath Tandamalle, Y.P.Reddy, A.K. Biradar et al," Mathematical model for estimation of strength and weld bead geometry of dissimilar metal laser welds," *International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM)*,2023
- [17]U, Ashoke Kumar, K. Kishore et al., "Multi Optimization of Friction Stir Welding of Aluminum AA 6061 Alloy using Grey based Taguchi Methods, BSPPublications, 2023
- [18]Hambeer Singh, Satish Sharma, Ashish Yadav,"Taguchi Parametric Optimization of Mild Steel Weld-Strength in Arc Welding Process" *International Journal of Scientific Research in Engineering and Management*, ISBN: 1955-2505, 2024
- [19]A. AnithaLakshmi, Bandhavi Challa et al., "Friction stir welding of aluminum AA6061 & AA8011 using optimization approach based on both Taguchi and grey relational analysis" ISBN: 2331-1916, 2024
- [20]Govind Aryan, "Optimization of Welding Parameters for Minimizing Defects and Porosity in Electric Arc Welding of Mild Steel Grade Fe 500 Using of Taguchi Method" *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology (IJRASET)* ISBN: 2321-9653, 2024